

Some Minoan words reconstructed after syllabic signs of the Linear A demonstrate notorious resemblance with Proto-Yeniseian forms

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Abstract

In Linear A, a schematic image of an object or being whose name began with a certain syllable was used to express that syllable. The Minoan language (the language of Linear A) is a dialect of Hattic. Within the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily, Hattic is quite close to the Yeniseian languages. In some cases, Minoan forms are closer to Yeniseian than to Hattic. For example, the Minoan word "to go" begins with the syllable *ye*, while the Hattic word "to go" is *nu*. The Proto-Yeniseian word "to go" is **hejV*; the Minoan form is closer to Proto-Yeniseian than to Hattic. The reconstructed Minoan word "to protect" is **qepV*. This form is closer to Proto-Yeniseian **qepVn* "to close the door" than to Hattic **kip* "to protect". The Minoan word "head" begins with the syllable *se*; it is closer to Proto-Yeniseian **c[i]ʔG* "head" than to Hattic **kaš* or **kiš* "head".

Keywords: Minoan language; Yeniseian languages; Ainu-Minoan macrofamily; Sino-Caucasian family; comparative linguistics

1. Introduction to the problem

Syllabic signs of the Linear A were created according to the acrophonic principle: to express a certain syllable a schematic image of an object or a being whose name began with that syllable was used.

Also, it is important to note that the Minoan language (the language of Linear A) is a dialect of Hattic, and that the Hattic language can be immediately used to understand Minoan texts (Akulov 2017b, 2021a, 2021b, 2023a, 2023b, 2024b, 2024c; Desherieva 2025, 2026b).

Syllabic signs of the Linear A and the corresponding Hattic words help to reconstruct Minoan words.

For instance, the Linear A sign for the syllable *wa* is a schematic depiction of a pile dwelling (Akulov 2017a: 22, Fig.1). It means that the Minoan word for "house" begins with the syllable *wa*. The Hattic word "house" is *wa_oel*, and this correlates well with the fact that Minoan word for "house" begins with *wa* (Akulov 2017a: 24). And thus, the Minoan word "house" most probably had the following view: **ware* (Akulov 2017a: 24).

Fig. 1. Sign “house” / “pile dwelling” expressing the syllable *wa*: left is the sign 24 of the Phaistos disc which is a schematic depiction of pile dwelling, and right is the corresponding sign of Linear A (A 54) (image source – Akulov 2017a: 24)

The signs of the Phaistos disc and the signs of Linear A are variants of the same writing system, serving the same language, but not different writing systems serving different languages (Akulov 2016, 2024a).

Another notorious example is the case of the Minoan word “to protect” which is connected with the sign “shield” (see Fig. 2).

Sign 56 of the Linear A expresses the syllable *qe*, this sign is a schematic depiction of shield.

And the Minoan word “shield” evidently begins with the syllable *qe*, and this fact correlates well with the fact that the Hattic word “to protect” is *kip*¹. And thus it is possible to say that the Minoan word “shield”/“to protect” probably had the following view: **qepV* (Akulov 2017a: 25).

Fig. 2. Sign “shield” expressing the syllable *qe*: left is the sign of the Phaistos disc which is a schematic depiction of shield, and right is the corresponding sign of Linear A (A78) (image source – Akulov 2017a: 25)

At present, there is complete certainty that the sign 56 of Linear A is an image of a shield, because this sign is a component of the logogram denoting armorer (see Desherieva 2026b: 30, Akulov 2024c: 20, and Fig. 3).

It is quite logical that the Minoan language is a dialect of Hattic and is close to Hattic, but in some cases the Minoan language turns out to be closer to the Yeniseian languages than to Hattic.

Recently it was shown that within the Sino-Caucasian (Ainu-Minoan) macrofamily the Hattic language is quite close to the Yeniseian languages, but not to Northwest Caucasian as it was usually supposed (Desherieva 2026a). And therefore it is quite logical that the Minoan language can demonstrate similarities with the Yeniseian languages.

¹ Soysal 2004: 288.

Fig. 3. The logogram “armor” containing the sign “shield” in the inscription of HT 89 (original image source – Linear A. 2026a)

2. Some Minoan words turn out to be closer to Proto-Yeniseian words than to Hattic

In some cases, the reconstructed Minoan words turn out to be closer to the Proto-Yeniseian forms than to Hattic.

2.1. The word “axe”

Linear A sign $\begin{matrix} \text{H} \\ | \end{matrix}$ expresses the syllable *a*, and is a schematic depiction of a double axe (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Left is Linear A sign 08, right is a Minoan votive double axe (right image source – Wikipedia 2026)

We do not yet know the Hattic words for "axe" or "to cut" / "to chop", but we know Proto-Yeniseian forms meaning "to cut", "to hack", and among them there is such a form as **ʔat* "to hack"² – this form perfectly corresponds to the fact that in Minoan the word "axe" begins with the syllable *a*. And it is possible to conclude that the Minoan word for "axe" had the following view: **atV* or **adV*.

2.2. The word "to go"

The sign 46 of Linear A expresses the syllable *je* (*ye*), this sign is a schematic representation of a walking person. This sign correlates with sign 01 of the Phaistos disc (see Fig. 4)

Fig. 4. Sign 01 of the disc (left) and sign 46 *je* (*ye*) of Linear A (image source – Akulov 2024a: 9)

The Minoan form "to go" evidently begins with the syllable *je* (*ye*).

The Hattic form for "to go", "to come" is *nu* (**na* / **nw*) (Soysal 2004: 297), and other forms for "to go" / "to come" are unknown.

² Starostin 2005a.

On the other hand, we have the Proto-Yeniseian form **hejVŋ* “to go”³. This form correlates quite well with the fact that the Minoan word “to go” began with the syllable *je* (*ye*). Also, it is important to note that in the Minoan spell against *samauna* disease the verb stem “to approach” has the view of *ya* (*ja*) / *ye* (*je*) (Akulov 2023a: 5).

Thus, it is possible to reconstruct the Minoan word for “to go” as **ye*, and this form evidently is more similar to the Proto-Yeniseian than to Hattic.

2.3. The word “grain” / “bread”

The Linear A sign 77 *ka* is a schematic depiction of bread. Bread of this shape was baked throughout the Mediterranean from the Bronze Age till the time of Roman Empire (Desherieva 2026b: 28 – 31, also see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Linear sign *ka* and a sample of ancient Egyptian bread (image source – Rubel 2021)

It means that the Minoan word “bread” begins with the syllable *ka*.

Also, it is important that in the inscription of HT 102 which is about distribution of food supplies to different professional groups; among other food supplies is mentioned such a product as *i-ka* (Fig. 6).

A. Akulov pointed out that in the text of HT 102 there is the word-form *i-ka* meaning “that grain”: in this word-form can be singled out the prefix *i-* that correlates well with the Hattic prefix *i-* that expresses the function of definite article, and the rest part of the word-form *ika* is its root – *ka* that correlates with the Hattic word *kait* “grain” (Akulov 2024c: 6).

And it is noteworthy that this word *i-ka* is written with the use of the sign *ka* .

I suppose that it is more correct to translate the root *ka* as “bread”, not “grain”, but, it is connected with the Hattic word *kait* “grain”.

However, Minoan *ka* “bread” is more similar to Proto-Yeniseian **qoK-* “hail” which is a cognate of the Proto-Sino-Tibetan form **kōk* “grain”⁴ than to Hattic *kait*.

³ Starostin 2005d.

⁴ Starostin 2005f.

Fig. 6. The word *i-ka* in the text of HT 102 (source of the original image – Linear A 2026b)

2.4. The word “head” or “hair”

The linear A sign 09 se is a schematic depiction of a head with a mohawk hairstyle. This sign correlates with the sign 02 of the Phaistos disc – “plumed head” (Fig. 7)

Fig. 7. Sign 02 of the Phaistos disc (left) and sign 09 se of the Linear A (right)

The fact that the Linear A sign expressing the syllable *se* is a schematic depiction of head means that the Minoan word for “head” could begin with the syllable *se*. The Hattic word for “head” is *kaš*, *kiš* (*keš* / *teiš*)⁵, while the Proto-Yeniseian word “head” is **c[i]ʔG*-⁶ and the Proto-Yeniseian word “hair” is **cəŋe*⁷. Forms **c[i]ʔG*- and **cəŋe* evidently are cognates. I suppose it is quite evident that the Minoan word for “head” is more similar to the Proto-Yeniseian **c[i]ʔG*- and **cəŋe* than to Hattic *kaš* and *kiš*. And therefore it is possible to state that the Minoan word for “head” was **sekV* or **senV*.

2.5. The word “shield”

As it has been noted above the reconstructed Minoan word “shield” / “to protect” is **qepV* (Akulov 2017a: 25). This reconstructed Minoan form is more similar to Proto-Yeniseian **qepVn*- “close the door”⁸, than to Hattic *kip* “to protect” (Soysal 2004: 288).

3. Conclusion

The fact that in some cases Minoan forms demonstrate more similarity with Proto-Yeniseian rather than Hattic is entirely logical and ties in well with the fact that the Minoan language started to separate from the ancient Hattian language on a quite early stage and that the Minoans for a long time lived in rather isolation, and due to this the Minoan language better preserved the more ancient forms.

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⁵ Soysal 2004: 286.

⁶ Starostin 2005c.

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